

AGRICULTURAL LAND ABANDONMENT IN LATVIA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FARMERS' CHOICE

Inga Grinfelde and Erik Mathijs*

Centre for Agricultural and Environmental Economics
Catholic University of Leuven
Willem de Croylaan 42
3001 Leuven
Belgium
telephone: +32 16 321558
fax: +32 16 321996
Inga.Grinfelde@agr.kuleuven.ac.be

Abstract

Latvian agriculture has experienced a transition from a central planning system to a market economy with surplus production, unstable market conditions, limited resources, etc. Concurrently with the transition, land is increasingly being abandoned. From 16% in 1997 to 21.2% in 2002 of total agricultural land was estimated to be unused. While being the result of an economic decision, agricultural abandonment of marginal land generally has an undesirable effect on environmental parameters, such as soil degradation. This paper reports the results of a survey (n=200) carried out in ten villages in the Cesis district in the northeast of Latvia. Farmers' behavior towards land abandonment was modeled using a two-step approach of Structural Equation Modeling. Variables affecting the share of land allocated for abandonment were summarized in nine factors. We find that short and long-term farm management decisions, farm income, land price, social capital, personal characteristics and the physical conditions of the land all have a significant effect on the amount of abandoned land. These results suggest that the low profitability of farming and the low quality of land, both mentioned as the prime reasons for land abandonment by the farmers themselves, are not the only reasons for land abandonment. In fact, land abandonment is part of a more complex of factors related to the management of the farm.

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1. Introduction

Latvian agriculture has experienced a transition from a central planning system to a market economy with surplus production, unstable market conditions, limited resources, etc. This transition has induced important changes in Latvian farming (Busmanis et al., 2001). The transformation of Latvian agriculture, which started in 1990, was characterized by two main elements: a change in land tenure and ownership (i.e. land reform) and the redistribution of non-land assets of collective farms to private farmers (Busmanis, 1999).

As a result of land privatisation the area of abandoned land has increased and soil fertility has declined during transition. Reduced liming has led to the acidification of agricultural soils. The decline of drainage systems maintenance has led to the destruction of drainage systems and disturbed soil moisture conditions. The deterioration of soil fertility has been associated with a general decrease in agricultural production and a shift from state and collective enterprises to small-scale and subsistence farming. As a consequence of privatization, the farm structure has become increasingly fragmented. Agricultural land abandonment has rapidly increased by a rate of 2% per year to peak at 21.2 % of total agricultural land area in 2002 (Busmanis et al., 2002; Latvian Ministry of Agriculture, 2001, 2002, 2003).

Important side effects of land abandonment include the destruction of drainage systems and the degradation of water ecosystems. Drainage effects caused by abandonment influence large areas of neighbour farmers' agricultural land and are irreparable. The process of self-renaturalisation of abandoned land may lead to impoverished biodiversity and atypical rural landscapes (Latvian Ministry of Agriculture, 2000).

This goal of this paper is to explore which factors influence the abandonment of land by farmers. Section 2 proposes a conceptual model of land abandonment. Section 3 discusses the data and variables used in the analysis. Section 4 describes the methodology used to analyze the factors influencing land abandonment at the farm level. Section 5 provides and discusses the results of the analysis and section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Conceptual model

To investigate the factors influencing land abandonment (ABAN), we propose the following conceptual model as a mix of endogenous and exogenous factors (figure 1). We have identified four sets of exogenous factors:

- **PERSONAL:** the personal characteristics of the farm manager and his/her family, such as education, age and family size. These tend to affect the opportunity cost of investing effort in land. However, the effects can be mixed. For example, better educated farmers are more likely to find off-farm employment, but at the same time they are more productive.
- **PROPERTY:** property issues referring to the source of land and thus tenure security. Farmers invest less effort in land they do not own (see e.g. Cole and Johnson, 2002). Sources of land include inheritance, privatization of collective farms, land sales market and leasing.
- **PHYSICAL:** the physical conditions of the land (parcel size, land improvements, etc.) affect its price and its opportunity costs. Too small parcels may be unfit for mechanisation and thus left unused.
- **HISTORICAL:** degree of fragmentation due to historical land patterns. In Latvia land property rights were restituted to the former owners. As a result, land ownership is extremely fragmented, and fields may be located in a different village.

We further identified four endogenous factors that may be affected by the exogenous factors and that influence management decisions:

- **INCOME:** the share of family income from farming. Off-farm income can also have mixed effects: it may relax liquidity constraints and thus contribute to the development of the farm or it may be an indication that off-farm activities are more profitable and that no effort is invested in the farm.
- **LANDPRICE:** the price of land. A higher land price will increase the land's opportunity costs and thus reduce land abandonment.
- **SOCIAL:** the social capital of the farmer, reflected by information sources, memberships and networks. The effect of social capital is expected to be ambiguous: social capital may increase productivity and thus opportunity costs of land, but at the same time social capital may increase off-farm opportunities.

We explicitly model management decisions as part of the conceptual model. Clearly, they are also endogenous factors in the model. We make a distinction between short term or tactical management decisions (SHORTRUN) and long term or strategic management decisions (LONGRUN).

Taking into account all possible direct and indirect effects yields 30 logical relations to be tested.

3. Data and variables

We collected data from a random sample of 200 farmers from ten villages in the Cesis district, which is located in the northeast of Latvia. It is a region characterised by relatively high rates of agricultural land abandonment (30.4% of total agricultural land in 2001). In each village, we randomly selected 20 farmers who dispose over at least 5 hectares of land. Households that did not cultivate any agricultural land were excluded. The main purpose of the survey

was to collect data on farmers' choice toward land abandonment and on the explanatory variables affecting land abandonment behavior.

The variables retained in the analysis along with some simple statistics are presented in Table 1. The following indices and transformations were made:

- LIVESTOCK was computed using a methodology developed by Busmanis (1999). First, the total amount of livestock units was calculated applying the following weights: cattle (0.6), pigs (0.15), sheep (0.07), goats (0.07), horses (0.04), poultry (0.01) and rabbit (0.01). Next, this index the amount of livestock units by total agricultural land.
- AGETECH equals one divided by the age of tractor and for farms who do not have a tractor; a zero was imputed if the farm did not have a tractor.
- SOCACT represents the degree of social activity of farmer and is the sum of six dummy variables: membership of nongovernmental organizations, membership of political organizations, membership of a local municipality council, having friendly relationships with neighbours, cooperation with neighbours and membership of some local amateur collective body.
- INFORMAT is the sum of the sources used (TV, radio, Press, Seminars, Agricultural adviser services, neighbors, other) and the issues for each source of information investigated (new technologies, Environmental protection, Subsidy, SAPARD, Market demand, possibilities to sell production, other). Farmers were asked to tick which information sources they used for each information issue.

4. Methodology

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is an appropriate statistical technique for this study. SEM is a multivariate technique combining aspects of multiple regression and factor analysis to

estimate a series of separate, but interdependent equations simultaneously with statistical efficiency (Hair et al., 1998; Joreskog and Sorbom, 1993). The measurement of constructs and the hypothesized relationships among constructs were examined by using SEM. This statistical technique is appropriate for the analysis of construct relationships by first validating the observed variables of the construct, and second, by determining the relationships among the constructs (Hoyle, 1995).

SEM consists of two stages: a measurement model and a structural model. The measurement model specifies how latent variables or hypothetical constructs depend upon the observed variables (Joreskog and Sorbom, 1993). The structural equation model specifies the causal relationships among the latent variables, describes the causal effects, and assigns explained and unexplained variance (Joreskog and Sorbom, 1993). The major focus of this technique is “the fit of the model”, which estimates the degree of correspondence between the specified relationships and those indicated by the data. The pattern of relationships stated in the specified model is compared to the pattern of relationships expressed by the data (Hair et al., 1998). Model fit in structural equation modeling helps to assess the adequacy of measured constructs and their relationships precisely and to yield a thorough understanding of the data (Hugh, et. al., 1986).

We used the following approach (Anderson and Gerbing 1988). First, we standardized and normalized all observed variables, because we wanted to give equal weights to all variables. Secondly, using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) we separately established the validity of each latent construct. Third, we extracted factor scores for each latent construct. Finally, the structural model then estimated the relationships between all constructs.

The proposed structural model in this study comprises 4 exogenous constructs (personal factors, historical factors, property issues and physical factors) and 6 endogenous

constructs (social activity, farm income, land price, long-term farm management decisions, short-term farm management decisions and amount of abandoned land).

4.1. Step 1: Measurement model

It is not possible to assess the meaning of one's terms in a theory without considerations of the relationship between unobservable and empirical concepts. It is considered important because one's ability to assess and interpret theories ultimately rests on the fidelity of measurements (Bagozzi and Phillip, 1982). A measurement model determines how well the observed indicators describe the latent variable as a measurement instrument. The researcher can assess how well the scale measures the concept in a measurement model (Hair et al., 1998). Confirmatory Factor Analysis was utilized to estimate the adequacy of the measurement model for each construct. The adequacy of the model indicated the goodness-of-fit between the hypothesized model and the sample data.

A minimum sample size is five observations for each estimated parameter (Hair et al., 1998). A total of 39 parameters for the structural model were estimated, and thus the minimum sample size should be 195. Thus the sample size for this study should exceed 195. The sample size of this study was 200; therefore the sample size of this study satisfied the minimum recommended level.

A reliable measure can be established when a measure is free from error and provides consistent results (Zikmund, 1997, 2000). Reliability applies when a measure shows the same results over time and across situations. All measures in the survey need to show the adequate internal consistency of the items. Internal consistency indicates the extent to which the individual items correlate with one another (Hatcher, 1994). The most popular measure of reliability is Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951; Peter, 1979). Cronbach's alpha indicates the degree to which error variance is present in a scale (Cronbach, 1970). Although Alpha

provides a conservative estimate of a measure's reliability (Carmines and Zeller, 1979), a coefficient alpha cannot ensure unidimensionality (Hair et al., 1998; Hatcher, 1994). The reliability of a scale can never be lower than alpha (Carmines and Zeller, 1979). Cronbach's alpha is closely related to reliability estimates based on the split-halves method (Carmines and Zeller, 1979). The coefficient alpha depends on the average inter-item correlation and the number of items in the scale. Cronbach's alpha is its positive relationship to the number of items in the scale (Hair et al., 1998). Nunnally (1967, 1978) suggests that reliability coefficients above .70 are generally considered acceptable. However, this is only a rule of thumb, and the social science literature does sometimes report studies employing variables with coefficient alpha reliabilities under .70 and sometimes even under .60 (Hatcher, 1994). It may decrease to .60 in exploratory research (Hair et al., 1998). Cronbach's Alpha should fall between .70 and .90 for a narrow construct, between .55 and .70 for a moderately broad construct, and between .35 and .55 for a very broad construct (Powell, 1992).

Table 2 reports the standardized coefficient for each item and a composite reliability for each construct. As the reliability estimates ranged from 0.40 to 0.57 for the four latent constructs in the model, we decided to include all four broad constructs in full model. However, our study is exploratory and also different types of variables (continuous ordinal or binary) were included in the factors. For example, in PERSONAL we included age as a continuous and education as an ordinal variable. Overall, the results indicate that the measurement model is appropriate for use with the full structural model. The final measures used for the various constructs are reported in the Table 2. Instead of arbitrarily constraining the factor loading of one item to unity we constrained the variance of the common factor to unity, i.e., all factor loadings were freely estimated. An iterative process was used to specify

factor models on the basis of both content and statistical considerations (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). The results are as follows (table 2)¹:

- Six factors were measured only with one observed variable. The factors ABAN, LANDPRICE and INCOME were defined only by one variable each. After running the CFA, we decided that the variable PARCELS best describes the factor HISTORICAL, LIVESTOCK best describes the factor SHORTRUN and BOUGHT the factor PROPERTY.
- The CFA retained 7 variables (FARMSIZE, INSURANCE, AGETECH, EQUIPMENT, SUBSIDY, ONFARM and LARGECOM) to describe long-term farm management decisions (LONGRUN). Maximum likelihood parameter estimation was used and a satisfactory fit for the factor measurement model was achieved (The χ^2 was 15.27, the df was 14, the p-value was 0.36, the RMSEA was 0.028, the NFI was 0.90, the NNFI was 0.98, the CFI was 0.99, the GFI was 0.98).
- Four variables (INFORMAT, SOCACT, KNOWSCHO and KNOWFARM) were retained to describe the social capital of the farmer (SOCIAL). Maximum likelihood parameter estimation was used and a satisfactory fit for the factor measurement model was achieved (the χ^2 was 0.22, the df was 2, the p-value was 0.89, the RMSEA was 0.000, the NFI was 1.00, the NNFI was 1.00, the CFI was 1.00, the GFI was 1.00).

¹ Possible goodness-of-fit statistics in CFA include Chi-square, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Goodness-of-fit Index (GFI). A careful consideration is that assessing the goodness-of-fit of a model is more a relative process than one with absolute criteria (Hair et al., 1998). A chi-square is used to test the closeness of fit between the unrestricted sample covariance and the restricted covariance matrix. A non-significant chi-square indicates that the hypothesized model is well fitted to the sample data. However, chi-square is significantly influenced by sample size so that the significance test of chi-square should not be considered as one with absolute criteria. The RMSEA estimates the error of approximation in the population, and represents how well the sample data fit the population covariance matrix. Values as high as .08 represent a reasonable fit. A lower value than .08 is recommended. The NFI takes into account the relative comparison of the proposed model to the null model. It is a measure ranging from 0 (no fit at all) to 1 (perfect fit). The recommended level is .90 or greater. The NNFI combines a measure of parsimony into a comparative index between the proposed and null models, resulting in values ranging from 0 to 1 (Hair et al., 1998). The recommended value is 0.90 or greater. The CFI indicates comparisons between the estimated model and a null or independence model. The values lie between 0 (no fit at all) and 1 (perfect fit); a value of at least 0.90 is recommended. The GFI is a measure of the relative amount of variance and covariance in the sample that is jointly explained by the sample. A value more than 0.90 indicates an acceptable fit to the data (Byrne, 1998).

- PHYSICAL was described by three variables (AGRPROP, FIELDSIZ and MELPROP). However, one factor model with three observed variables is just identified and for just identified models it is not possible to calculate goodness of fit statistics.
- PERSONAL was described by three variables (-AGE, EDUCATION and FAMILYSIZE). In the final model, we included age multiplied by (-1) to avoid negative factor loadings.

4.2. Step 2: Structural model

The maximum likelihood method was employed in the estimation of this structural equation model. Maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) is a commonly used and conservative method that iteratively improves parameter estimates to minimize a specific fit function (Hair et al., 1998). The structural model is the regression part of the latent variables. It specifies the links among the unobserved latent variables. It specifies which latent variables directly or indirectly influence changes in the values of other latent variables in the model (Byrne, 1998). The original theoretical structural model is presented in Figure 2.

We employed a system of six simultaneous equations to estimate the coefficients of the structural model. The first equation suggests that the proportion of abandoned land is a function of short term farm management decisions, long term farm management decisions, social capital, personal characteristic, historical factors, physical land characteristics, property issues, share of income from farming and the land price:

$$\begin{aligned}
 ABAN = & \gamma_{11} * SHORTRUN + \gamma_{12} * LONGRUN + \gamma_{13} * SOCIAL + \beta_{14} * PERSONAL \\
 & + \beta_{15} * PROPERTY + \beta_{16} * HISTORICAL + \beta_{17} * PHYSICAL + \gamma_{18} * LANDPRICE \\
 & + \gamma_{19} * INCOME + \zeta_1
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

The second equation states that the short-term farm management decisions are a function of long term farm management decisions, social capital, personal characteristics, historical factors, physical land factors, property issues, share of income from farming and land prices:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SHORTRUN} = & \gamma_{21} * \text{LONGRUN} + \gamma_{22} * \text{SOCIAL} + \beta_{23} * \text{PERSONAL} + \beta_{24} * \text{PROPERTY} \\ & + \beta_{25} * \text{HISTORICAL} + \beta_{26} * \text{PHYSICAL} + \gamma_{27} * \text{LANDPRICE} + \gamma_{28} * \text{INCOME} + \zeta_2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The third equation states that the long term farm management decisions are influenced by social capital, personal characteristics, historical factors, physical land factors, property issues, the share of income from farming and land prices:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LONGRUN} = & \gamma_{31} * \text{ACTIVITY} + \beta_{32} * \text{PERSONAL} + \beta_{33} * \text{PROPERTY} \\ & + \beta_{34} * \text{HISTORICAL factor} + \beta_{35} * \text{PHYSICAL factor} + \gamma_{36} * \text{LANDPRICE} \\ & + \gamma_{37} * \text{INCOME} + \zeta_3 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The fourth equation states that the land price is a function of historical factors, physical factors and property issues:

$$\text{LANDPRICE} = \beta_{41} * \text{PROPERTY} + \beta_{42} * \text{HISTORICAL} + \beta_{43} * \text{PHYSICAL} + \zeta_4 \quad (4)$$

The fifth equation states that the share of income from farming is influenced by social capital and personal characteristics:

$$\text{INCOME} = \gamma_{51} * \text{SOCIAL} + \beta_{52} * \text{PERSONAL} + \zeta_5 \quad (5)$$

Finally, the sixth equation states that social capital is a function of personal characteristics:

$$\text{SOCIAL} = \beta_{61} * \text{PERSONAL} + \zeta_6 \quad (6)$$

5. Results

Table 3 reports the correlations between each latent variable. Figure 3 presents the completely standardized path coefficients for the initial structural model. Goodness of fit for the initial

model was acceptable (The χ^2 was 8.17, the df was 9, the p-value was 0.52, the RMSEA was 0.00, the NFI was 0.98, the NNFI was 1.01, the CFI was 1.00, the GFI was 0.99). However, in this model many effects were not significant. The initial structural model was revised step by step by deleting non-significant paths and by adding the path from PHYSICAL to INCOME. From the revised model we excluded LANDPRICE because this factor did not have a significant relationship with other factors. The goodness of fit for the revised model is acceptable (The χ^2 was 20.83, the df was 17, the p-value was 0.23, the RMSEA was 0.031, the NFI was 0.95, the NNFI was 0.98, the CFI was 0.99, the GFI was 0.98). Figure 4 presents the standardized coefficients estimated by the revised model.

The direct effects are the straightforward impact of one variable on another that is not mediated by any other variable. Indirect effects are influences that are mediated by at least one other variable. The total effects are the sum of the direct and indirect effects. The effects were tested on the basis of the revised structural model. The results are presented in Table 4. We will discuss only the total effect on the amount of abandoned land. The revised structural model specified the direct and indirect effects among the exogenous and endogenous variables. The following results are obtained:

- The share of income from farming is positively affected by social capital and the physical characteristics of the land. Socially active farmers can easier find new possibilities to sell production and they are well informed. Farms with a higher proportion of agricultural land, bigger fields and higher proportion of ameliorated land have higher farm income.
- Long run investment decisions are positively affected by the share of income from farming, by social capital and by favourable historical conditions. Farmers with high farm income are more interested to invest in their farm than farmers with low farm income. Socially active farmers have more information about new technologies and

other possibilities to get more income from farming. Farms with larger amount of parcels have more land and they are more willing to make long run investments.

- Short run production decisions are positively affected by long run investment decisions and by the share of income from farming, but negatively by the physical characteristics of the land. As short run production decisions are proxied by the number of livestock units per ha, farms that make long run investments and are interested to enlarge farming will also keep more animals. Also farmers with higher - farm income are more interested to enlarge their herd. However, livestock farms with grazing animals do not need such good physical conditions of agricultural land as arable farms.
- Land abandonment is positively affected by favourable property conditions and by favourable physical characteristics of the land, but negatively affected by longrun and shortrun management decisions. The positive effect of favourable property conditions on land abandonment can be explained by the fact that during the last years land has become a profitable (even speculative) investment, as land prices are low. This may explain why land with good physical characteristics is abandoned. However, farmers who make long run investments and have a large herd do not abandon their agricultural land because they are interested to increase farming.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we explored how various factors influence the amount of abandoned land, and the intermediate mechanisms by which they do so. We find that short and long-term farm management decisions, farm income, land price, social capital, personal characteristics and the physical conditions of the land all have a significant effect on the amount of abandoned land. These results suggest that the low profitability of farming and the low quality of land,

both mentioned as the prime reasons for land abandonment by the farmers themselves, are not the only reasons for land abandonment. In fact, land abandonment is part of a more complex of factors related to the management of the farm.

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Table 1: Simple statistics of dependent and independent variables

Variable	Definition of variable	Mean	Std Dev	Max	Min
LIVESTOCK	Index of livestock units per ha	0.26	0.32	1.88	0.00
CULTIVATED	Share of cultivated land in total agricultural land	0.13	0.18	1.00	0.00
FARMSIZE	Total farm size	42.67	56.42	694.20	5.00
ORGANIC	Dummy equals one if organic farming is practiced (without chemicals)	0.65	0.48	0	1
DEBT	Dummy equals one if the farmer has outstanding loan at the bank	0.15	0.36	0	1
INSURANCE	Dummy equals one if the farmer has any insurance on agricultural assets	0.10	0.30	1.00	0.00
EQUIPMENT	Dummy equals one if the farmer has enough equipment	0.38	0.49	1.00	0.00
SUBSIDY	Dummy equals one if the farm is getting subsidies	0.56	0.50	1.00	0.00
ONFARM	Dummy equals one if the farmer sells any production on the farm	0.27	0.44	1.00	0.00
LARGECOM	Dummy equals one if the farmer sells production to a large processing company	0.41	0.49	1.00	0.00
AGETECH	One divided by the age of the tractor	0.07	0.12	1.00	0.00
KNOWPARE	Dummy equals one if the farmer learned farming skills from parents	0.53	0.50	1.00	0.00
KNOWCOLL	Dummy equals one if manager learned farming from work in collective farm	0.57	0.50	1.00	0.00
KNOWSCHO	Dummy equals to one if manager learned farming from school	0.26	0.44	1.00	0.00
KNOWFARM	Dummy equals to one if manager learned farming from other farmers	0.32	0.47	1.00	0.00
KNOWSELF	Dummy equals to one if manager learned farming from own experience	0.77	0.42	1.00	0.00
SOCACT	Index of social activity	1.79	0.79	4.00	0.00
INFORMAT	Sum of information source and information issue matrix	13.54	8.21	41.00	0.00
LANDPRICE	Land price in LVL/ha	127.29	45.38	418.00	71.00
ABAN	Amount of abandoned land, ha	5.24	11.30	105.20	0.00
INCOMESHARE	Share of total family income that comes from farming	27.77	31.07	100.00	0.00
AGE	Age of the farm manager	51.61	13.40	83.00	27.00
GENDER	Gender of the farm manager	0.59	0.49	1.00	0.00
EDUCATION	Level of education with following scores: (1) basic; (2) secondary non-agriculture; (3) secondary in agriculture; (4) university non-agriculture; (5) university non-agriculture; (6) postgraduate	2.60	1.18	6.00	1.00
FAMILY SIZE	Number of family members living on the farm	3.52	1.72	10.00	1.00
BOUGHT	Amount of land bought, ha	12.25	54.13	694.20	0.00
CITY	Distance from district center, Cesis	50.60	9.68	70.00	26.00
PARCELS	Number of parcels	2.63	2.24	17.00	1.00
DISTANCE	Number of kilometers from home until furthest parcel	2.98	3.64	20.00	0.00
KEEPLAND	Dummy equals one if the land owner decided not to sell any land	0.94	0.24	1.00	0.00
AGRPROP	Share of agricultural land in total land area	0.49	0.24	1.00	0.02
MELPROP	Amount of ameliorated land divided by agricultural land	0.41	0.43	1.00	0.00
FIELDSIZ	Average size of fields, ha	3.74	4.16	30.00	0.00
MEDPROP	Amount of meadows divided by agricultural	0.14	0.22	1.00	0.00

Variable	Definition of variable	Mean	Std Dev	Max	Min
	land				
PASTROP	Amount of pastures divided by agricultural land	0.21	0.28	1.00	0.00
FORESRPR	Amount of forests divided by total land	0.40	0.24	0.98	0.00

Table 2 Factor regression loadings, coefficients (lambda) and (St.Error), t-statistics and reliability values for the measurement model

Construct/ Indicator	Factor loading	Lambda (and St. error)	t- value	Reliability (Cronbach's alpha)
<i>ABAN</i>	1.00			
<i>LANDPRICE</i>	1.00			
<i>INCOME</i>	1.00			
<i>PROPERTY</i>				
BOUGHT	1.00			
<i>HISTORICAL</i>				
PARCELS	1.00			
<i>SHORTRUN</i>				
LIVESTOCK	1.00			
<i>LONGRUN</i>				<i>0.56</i>
FARMSIZE	0.05	0.15(0.086)	1.72	
INSURANCE	0.07	0.22(0.085)	2.59	
AGETECH	0.14	0.39(0.084)	4.60	
EQUIPMENT	0.10	0.29(0.085)	3.37	
SUBSIDY	0.47	0.72(0.088)	8.17	
ONFARM	0.17	0.43(0.084)	5.16	
LARGECOM	0.28	0.59(0.084)	6.93	
<i>SOCIAL</i>				<i>0.49</i>
INFORMAT	0.42	0.61(0.12)	5.31	
SOCACT	0.10	0.23(0.094)	2.42	
KNOWSCHO	0.19	0.38(0.094)	4.01	
KNOWFARM	0.37	0.58(0.11)	5.19	
<i>PHYSICAL</i>				<i>0.57</i>
AGRPROP	0.23	0.45(0.093)	4.80	
FIELDSIZ	0.37	0.59(0.11)	5.54	
MELPROP	0.42	0.63(0.11)	5.67	
<i>PERSONAL</i>				<i>0.40</i>
-AGE	0.81	0.85(0.36)	2.34	
EDUCATION	0.08	0.26(0.13)	2.00	
FAMILYSIZE	0.09	0.30(0.15)	2.08	

Table 3: Correlation matrix for endogenous and exogenous variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.SOCIAL	1.00									
2.LONGRUN	0.32	1.00								
3.PERSONAL	0.12	0.00	1.00							
4.PHYSICAL	0.07	0.05	0.05	1.00						
5.LANDPRICE	0.05	0.06	-0.01	-0.01	1.00					
6.ABAN	-0.10	-0.23	0.02	0.18	-0.08	1.00				
7.INCOME	0.24	0.61	0.09	0.16	-0.04	-0.18	1.00			
8.PROPERTY	0.00	0.04	0.09	0.00	-0.10	0.61	0.03	1.00		
9.HISTORICAL	0.05	0.19	0.12	0.06	0.03	0.33	0.11	0.47	1.00	
10.SHORTRUN	0.20	0.36	0.13	-0.16	0.00	-0.27	0.43	-0.08	-0.02	1.00

Table 4: Magnitude and significance of relationships

Latent Variable	Estimate (SE)	t-value	St. direct effects	St. indirect effects	St. total effects	R ²
<i>ABAND</i>						<i>0.46</i>
PERSONAL	-	-	-	-0.01	-0.01	
PHYSICAL	0.17(0.053)	3.26	0.18	0	0.18	
PROPERTY	0.60(0.052)	11.63	0.61	-	0.61	
HISTORICAL	-	-	-	-0.03	-0.03	
SOCIAL	-	-	-	-0.08	-0.08	
LONGRUN	-0.22(0.056)	-3.83	-0.22	-0.02	-0.23	
INCOME	-	-	-	-0.18	-0.18	
SHORTRUN	-0.12(0.056)	-2.10	-0.12		-0.12	
<i>LONGRUN</i>						<i>0.41</i>
PERSONAL	-	-	-	0.04	0.04	
PHYSICAL	-	-	-	0.08	0.08	
HISTORICAL	0.12(0.054)	2.18	0.12	-	0.12	
SOCIAL	0.18(0.056)	3.23	0.18	0.13	0.31	
INCOME	0.56(0.056)	9.96	0.56	-	0.56	
<i>SHORTRUN</i>						<i>0.25</i>
PERSONAL	-	-	-	0.02	0.02	
PHYSICAL	- 0.23(0.063)	-3.66	-0.23	0.07	-0.16	
HISTORICAL	-	-	-	0.02	0.02	
SOCIAL	-	-	-	0.13	0.13	
LONGRUN	0.13(0.078)	1.62	0.13	-	0.13	
INCOME	0.39(0.078)	5.00	0.39	0.07	0.46	
<i>INCOME</i>						<i>0.073</i>
PERSONAL	-	-	-	0.03	0.03	
PHYSICAL	0.15(0.069)	2.11	0.15	-	0.15	
SOCIAL	0.23(0.069)	3.29	0.23	-	0.23	
<i>SOCIAL</i>						<i>0.015</i>
PERSONAL	0.12(0.071)	1.74	0.12	-	0.12	

Figure 1: Conceptual model of land abandonment

Figure 2: Full Structural model with obtained standardized coefficients (bold indicates significance level ($p < 0.05$))

Figure 3 Revised model with obtained standardized coefficients (bold indicates significance level ($p < 0.05$))

